

Investigation of the Fatigue Behaviour of Some Industrial Glass Reinforced Polyesters (GRP)

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ABSTRACT

The experimental approach of the fatigue behaviour of glass-fibre reinforced polyesters has been carried out by means of torsion tests characterized by a constant strain amplitude.

The material failure has been assessed by means of curves of the relative variation of the torque depending on the number of cycles ; these curves also make it possible to define the fatigue strength diagram.

The effect of various hydric, thermal and mechanical environments on the fatigue strength of several polyester resin/glass-fibre compounds, is studied.

1 - INTRODUCTION -

Composite materials as glass reinforced polyesters are used since about thirty years for industrial products and since about twenty years in buildings.

In spite of this large application, there are still many problems not yet solved concerning for example the weathering, the mechanical behaviour and the variation of these characteristics when the material is exposed to repeated stresses. After having studied the first factor (1), the present contribution deals with the fatigue of GRP materials.

2 - EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS -

2-1 - Specimens -

The materials which have been examined in the course of this investigation are industrial polyester laminates (A,B,C) manufactured with three different resins reinforced with a glass mat.

- A - corresponds to a standard formulation of glycol-propylene maleophthalate, cross-linked by styrene, light-stabilised -
- B - has a good resistance to corrosion and is expected to have a better mechanical fatigue behaviour -
- C - is an HET based resin, i.e. with better fire resistance -

The reinforcement, of the order of 25% by weight consisted of 2 standard quality mats (450 g/m² and 300 g/m²). The specimens are left to polymerise for 24 hours at ambient temperature, followed by post-curing for 15 hours in a ventilated oven at 70°C. The samples are little bars with a length of 50 mm, a width of 5 mm and a thickness equal to 2 mm.

2-2 - Experimental installation and experimental conditions investigated -

The fatigue machine used for the investigation enables the loading of specimens in torsion (2).

The specimen, loaded in torsion, is subjected to a deformation of constant amplitude and it is possible to follow continuously the variation of stress to which the specimen is subjected during the test.

The amplitude of the deformation can be adjusted between 0,05% and 2% in relative deformation (α), which means, for a specimen with geometrical characteristics (l = 40 mm ; c = 5 mm ; a = 2 mm), an angle of torsion ϕ , in absolute value, of ± 1 to $\pm 45^\circ$ on either side of the position of equilibrium since

$$\alpha = \frac{a\phi}{2l} .$$

The torque is measured with a piezoelectric cell and a magnetic transducer for measuring displacement enables accurate control of the amplitude of the initial deformation.

This deformation varies alternatively with time and may be reasonably represented by an expression of the form $\alpha = \alpha_M \sin 2\pi Ft \pm \alpha_a$.

The frequency of the load (F) is maintained constant. It has been set at 5 Hz to avoid any uncontrolled thermal disturbance in the course of the tests (3)(4)(5).

α_a is a constant static deformation, corresponding also to the mean deformation over a period of time, to which the specimen is subjected during the test.

An experimental approach corresponding to a load with a mean deformation $\langle \alpha \rangle = \alpha_a$ not equal to zero has been achieved in the following conditions : for any

$$\alpha_M = (\alpha_i) = (0.5\%, 0.8\%, 1\%, 1.2\%, 1.4\%)$$

$$\alpha_a = (0\%, 0.2\%, \alpha_i \dots \alpha_M)$$

The influence of two types of environment has been assessed :

- . an atmosphere with air at normal hygrothermal values (50% R.H. at 20°C),

. water free of any corrosive admixtures or any other wetting agent, at a temperature of 20°C.

Finally a certain approach to the effect of temperature has been achieved by means of tests in which the specimens are kept successively in water at constant temperatures of 20°, 40°, 60° and 80°C.

2-3 - Parameters investigated, degradation indices -

Direct plotting of a Wöhler curve is fairly delicate on account of the great dispersion of the experimental results (fig. 1) ; consequently, we try to follow continuously the damage resulting from a number of fatigue cycles at a given constant deformation amplitude.

In fact the direct investigation of the fatigue phenomenon gives results that are inherently difficult to reproduce because the mechanical behaviour of composites which is very sensitive to a great number of intrinsic or extrinsic parameters (factors specific to the material ; shape factors ; conditions of loading and environment of the specimens ...) (6).

It's the reason why has been studied the effect of an artificially induced defect to concentrate the stresses in a given zone of the sample, so as to create a zone of great probability of failure. However, this part of the work was not found very conclusive (7) (8). The investigation of the mechanical behaviour of the material by mean of a dynamic torsion test has led us to define a first deterioration index : the shear modulus.

During this test, two parameters are accessible : the shear modulus G and the damping factor δ . It was found quite quickly that the spectrum of internal friction δ as a function of temperature was not affected by mechanical damage.

On the other hand, the shear modulus G decreases continuously as a function of the number of fatigue cycles according to a set of curves shown in fig. 2. This differential measurement of G provided a reference index for the progress of the damage (more particularly a reference for the measurement of the torque during the test). It is possible to record, by means of a suitable measuring cell, the progress of the maximum value of the torque to which the specimen is subjected during each cycle.

So the monitoring of the damage has been done either in terms of shear modulus or of the torque. The shape of curves C/C_0 or G/G_0 as a function of $\log N$, irrespective of α_M , is of a sigmoid type (fig. 2) and the tangent at the point of inflection or extrapolation of the nearly linear part of the curve, enables a definition of two parameters N_S and N_R . It is possible to define N_S as a threshold beyond which the material starts to accommodate the stress in an irreversible manner, i.e. to undergo some damage. N_R , defined by a graphical representation as in fig. 2, provides a good approach to the number of cycles at failure. This approach contributes considerably to reducing the measurement dispersion linked to the number of cycles at failure determination for a given maximum amplitude of deformation, i.e. the determination of the Wöhler curve corresponding to the experimental conditions of the investigation (fig. 1).

The study of the torque C_0 as a function of the torsion angle α and temperature has led us to set at 1.4% the maximum relative deformation imposed on the specimens during fatigue testing. 1,4% corresponds to the maximum

amplitude of the deformation on this side of which, the material presents a quasi-elastic mechanical behaviour, even after many cycles of fatigue.

Figure 1 - Endurance diagram showing the dispersion of experimental results with the direct approach $\alpha_M (\log N_R)(o)$ - Points (●) (■) correspond to extrapolated values (N_R and N_G) on the basis of the $G/G_0 (N)$ curves - (sample A ; test in air at 20°C) -

3 - EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMMENTS -

3-1 - Comparative study of fatigue behaviour in air and water -

Figures 2 and 3 show the fatigue behaviour of laminate A in air and in water. The set of curves obtained for different deformation amplitudes give a good representation of the behaviour of laminates in general, both in terms of the sigmoid shape of the profiles and in terms of the nearly homothetic regression of the curves according to the logarithm of the number of cycles.

A phenomenological model with three stages has been proposed elsewhere (9) ; this degradation pattern may be used to describe curves which are shown on the figures 2 and 3. In fact after extensive thresholds of no damage, stage I is more difficult to outline except for low amplitude deformations. Stage II, corresponding to progressive damage of the continuous phase of the laminate and of a number of fibres is well outlined. The existence of stage III is linked failure occurring, and, in some cases, stage III is clearly outlined whilst in others failure occurred as early as the end of stage II. Generally speaking, failure of the material is a random event occurring during the stage III that corresponds to stressing a specimen often partially failed already.

The number of cycles at the threshold of damage (N_S) and the number of cycles at failure (N_R), extrapolated from the previous curves are shown in next table.

α_M		0,5%	0,8%	1%	1,2%	1,4%
N_S	air	$17 \cdot 10^4$	$7 \cdot 10^3$	$11 \cdot 10^2$	140	42
	water	$7 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^3$	$4 \cdot 10^2$	45	21
N_R	air	$2 \cdot 10^{11}$	$1,5 \cdot 10^7$	$6 \cdot 10^6$	$1 \cdot 10^6$	$1,5 \cdot 10^5$
	water	$2 \cdot 10^9$	$6 \cdot 10^5$	$2,5 \cdot 10^5$	$3,5 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^4$

It may be seen that the overall pattern of points $\alpha_M(N_S)$ is practically independent of the environment in the test (air or water), other things being equal.

So this curve of first damage appears, at ambient temperature, as an intrinsic property of the material, independent of the external environment of the specimen during the test.

Finally one will note the aggressive affect of an aqueous medium. For a same deformation, the fatigue life is appreciably reduced when the laminate is tested in water than when it is tested in air :

Figure 2 - Relative variation of the torque C/C_0 as a function of the number of cycles N for various amplitudes of deformation - (sample A ; test in air at 20°C) -

Figure 3 - Relative variation of the torque C/C_0 as a function of the number of cycles N for various amplitudes of deformation - (sample A ; test in water at 20°C) -

3-2 - Influence of temperature on fatigue behaviour -

It should be recalled that, in order to understand the influence of temperature on the fatigue behaviour of a standard laminate (A), the $C/C_0(N,T)$ curves were plotted for a zero mean deformation, for specimen kept in water at different temperatures. The variations of the number of cycles at failure N_R and the number of cycles at the threshold of damage N_S will be considered as a function of temperature. Figures 4 and 5 show the corresponding curves which, of course, must be taken as simple profiles, taking account of the type of definition of each point. It is possible in this way to observe (fig. 4) similar variation profiles for the number of cycles at failure (N_R) as a function of temperature (T), irrespective of the amplitude of deformation. In fact, between the ambient temperature and 60°C , N_R remains approximately stable or decreases slightly before increasing very considerably with temperatures beyond 60° . On the other hand, in the range of temperatures investigated, N_S seems hardly affected by rising temperature, except for slight deformations ($\alpha_M \leq 0,8\%$) where N_S decreases with increasing temperature.

At constant amplitude of deformation, the torque, i.e. the induced stresses to which the specimens are subjected, is a decreasing function of temperature. This may provide an explanation of a certain increase of the number of cycles at failure N_R with temperature. As regards the number of cycles at the threshold of damage, N_S is a rapidly decreasing parameter down to an asymptotic limit when the maximum amplitude of deformation α_M increases. Moreover, N_S is directly linked to the start of the first stage of degradation of the composite material, i.e. to the damage to the fibre-resin bond.

When the temperature rises, the rigidity of the matrix, which distributes the stresses over the reinforcement, decreases to a much greater extent than the rigidity of the glass fibres. This is why the differential stresses at the interface between the two components are an increasing function of temperature and are the cause of accelerated damage of the coupling agent. The damage is more clearly marked when the amplitude of parameter N_S is greater, i.e. at low deformations.

Figure 4 - Variation of the number of cycles at failure N_R as a function of temperature for various amplitudes of deformation (sample A ; test in water)

Figure 5 - Variation of the number of cycles at the threshold of damage N_S as a function of temperature for various amplitudes of deformation - (sample A ; test in water)

3-3 - Influence of a mean deformation different from zero -

The experimental approach to this investigation has been outlined previously.

Figure 6 - Relative variation of the torque C/C_0 as a function of the number of cycles N for $\alpha_M = 1\%$ and a mean deformation α_a equal to 0.2% ; 0.5% ; 0.8% and 1% -

Figure 6 shows experimental measurements of the relative variation of torque C/C_0 as a function of the number of cycles N for one amplitude of sinusoidal deformation (α_M) and various static deformations (α_a).

It may be seen immediately that the general shape of the curves, with the exception of those for a low amplitude static deformation ($\alpha_a = 0,2\%$), is disturbed in relation to the classical diagram. The sequence of the various stages of damage of the laminates seems modified by the superimposition of a static deformation α_a on the sinusoidal component α_M of the alternating deformation.

The curves relative to pure waved deformation ($\alpha_a = \alpha_M$) always reflect extensive damage to the material right from the first cycles of stressing irrespective of the value of α_M .

Finally, whatever the value of $\alpha_a \neq 0$ a deformation α_M of great amplitude always gives rise, from the very start of the fatigue cycles, to damage that may correspond to partial or even total failure of the specimens. Consequently, it is difficult, not to say often impossible, to assess, even qualitatively, the influence of a mean stress different from zero on both the value of the threshold of damage N_S and the number of cycles at failure N_R .

3-4 - Comparative study of three industrial laminates -

The fatigue behaviour of the three industrial laminates A, B and C will be analysed to try to establish a ranking order of laminates according

to their capacity to withstand damage by fatigue in torsion in the experimental conditions of the investigation.

The following table gives the experimental results relating to the determination of parameters N_S and N_R of each of the three samples A, B and C, parameters plotted on the diagram in figure 7. The behaviour of A was described before. The profile of the damage curves $(C/C_0)\alpha_M(N)$ for materials B and C is identical with that of A.

			0,5%	0,8%	1%	1,2%	1,4%
A	N_S	air	$17 \cdot 10^4$	$7 \cdot 10^5$	$11 \cdot 10^2$	140	42
		water	$7 \cdot 10^4$	$5 \cdot 10^5$	$4 \cdot 10^2$	45	21
	N_R	air	$2 \cdot 10^{11}$	$1,5 \cdot 10^7$	$6 \cdot 10^6$	10^6	$1,5 \cdot 10^5$
		water	$2 \cdot 10^9$	$6 \cdot 10^5$	$2,5 \cdot 10^5$	$3,5 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^4$
B	N_S	air	=	$7 \cdot 10^5$	10^5	$5 \cdot 10^2$	$1,6 \cdot 10^2$
		water	=	$4 \cdot 10^5$	$7 \cdot 10^2$	$4 \cdot 10^2$	90
	N_R	air	=	10^7	$4 \cdot 10^5$	10^5	$4 \cdot 10^4$
		water	=	$1,5 \cdot 10^6$	$3,5 \cdot 10^5$	$3,5 \cdot 10^4$	10^4
C	N_S	air	$1,5 \cdot 10^5$	$6 \cdot 10^5$	$9 \cdot 10^2$	$4 \cdot 10^2$	$1,5 \cdot 10^2$
		water	$6 \cdot 10^5$	$7 \cdot 10^5$	10^3	$2 \cdot 10^2$	$1,2 \cdot 10^2$
	N_R	air	$3 \cdot 10^9$	$2,5 \cdot 10^6$	$3,5 \cdot 10^5$	$8 \cdot 10^4$	$7 \cdot 10^4$
		water	?	$9 \cdot 10^5$	$3 \cdot 10^5$	10^5	$3,5 \cdot 10^4$

Figure 7 - Endurance diagrams for various laminates A, B and C (tests in air).
 N.B. : the experimental results (α_M, N_S) are distributed over a single curve of first damage and there is close similarity in the behaviour of B and C (endurance curve (α_M, N_R) -

Examination of laminate B shows that the effect of water which is, of course, negligible on the values of N_S , reduces the number of cycles at failure N_R by a multiplication factor of the order of 5, irrespective of the value α_M .

It should be noted also that low deformations $\alpha_M \leq 0,5\%$ do not seem to cause any deterioration of the laminate, even after 10^8 fatigue cycles, whether the test is carried out in air or water.

The fatigue behaviour of C is closely similar to the one previously described for B, which led to a comparative analysis of the results shown in the previous table.

- . First of all, the points (α_M, N_G) seem to be on a curve of first damage that is the same for the three materials A, B or C, whatever the environment in which the specimens were tested.
- . Secondly, water causes a considerable reduction in the number of cycles at failure N_R for the various deformation amplitudes investigated, which, for a given deformation, may be reflected by a negative translation of the endurance curve of the order of $\log 25$ for sample A. This does not apply to samples B and C which show less sensitivity to the aggressive effects of water. In case B, a simple explanation may be found in the fact that the resin is a formulation based on heavy glycols with additional anti-corrosion properties. However, this is not the case for C, and this is perhaps just another example of a particular type of behaviour for this resin made from HET acid !
- . Finally the great fatigue strength shown by specimens B subjected to low amplitude deformations, may also be explained to a certain extent by the remark given above.

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